

THE CLASSIFICATION OF WORD CLASSES

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Annotation: In this article, the author examines the classification word classes and types. Besides, the author gives several activities and examples of the explanation of word classes.

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The various types of words employed in grammar are referred to as word classes, sometimes called parts of speech. Prepositions, pronouns, conjunctions, and other minor word classes exist in addition to the major word classes of nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. Understanding a word's class is essential to using it effectively since each word class has certain usage guidelines. According to Richard Nordquist a word class in English grammar is a group of words that share similar formal characteristics, particularly in distribution and inflections. The more formal term "part of speech" and the term "word class" are comparable. It is also known by many names, including syntactic category, lexical category, and grammatical category (though these concepts are not entirely synonymous).

The lexical (or open or form) classes, which include nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs, and the function (or closed or structure) classes, which include determiners, particles, prepositions, and others, are the two main word class families. (2019) Verbs deal with reflecting the action or state of some person or thing. Its function is to show some event in the present, past or future. It can be regular or irregular, stative or action. Regular verbs are words, which can be used by adding – ed, d in past and past participles, but irregular verbs are different from them in the sense of forming new words in past or past participles.

For example, to play means doing some enjoyable action. It is a regular verb. In the present simple tense, we use it like this; *I play the guitar on Mondays*. In past simple, we should add –ed at the end of the word. *e.g. I played the guitar last Monday*

The root of the word is not changed when we make up past tenses. But irregular verbs have other forms of one word in the past and past participle. *e.g. The verb to write means to note some word on some sheet of paper with a pen or pencil. I write messages to my friend every day. I wrote a message to my friend yesterday.*

Nouns are words, which refer to the name thing or person. In a sentence, it represents an action, an object, or a place where the action took place. *For example, a teacher should pay attention to his pupils' condition.* Nouns can be singular or plural, countable or uncountable. For example, the word ‘a book’ is singular and countable. We can count on it. The word ‘wood’ is uncountable, because this word reflects thing that shows material. In English, there are several words, which refer to uncountable nouns due to the impossibility of counting these objects one by one. They can be shown by words such as bread, butter, water, milk, soup, wood, gold, hair, furniture or love. We can use these words in singular with the help of some words showing containers such as tin, glass or words that give meaning to the amount of something. *For example, a piece of paper, a loaf of bread, a bar of chocolate etc.*

Adjectives are words that deal with characterizing of quality of nouns or pronouns giving the question ‘How? What kind of?’ *for example, a beautiful girl, a green flower, an interesting book, and tall men.* There are degrees of adjectives, such as comparative and superlative degrees. A comparative degree helps us to identify the difference between two nouns or pronouns. It forms by adding –er to regular adjectives that have no more two syllables, such as clever-cleverer, tall-taller

For example, my car is bigger than my friend's car.

We use the superlative to show that something is the best or the only one in a group that we want to pay attention to. To construct this degree we should add the suffix -est to the root of the adjective and put the definite article ‘the’.

For example, my friend is the cleverest person that I have seen in my life.

Irregular adjectives are words, which have comparative and superlative degrees in other unique words. For instance, good-better-the best, bad-worse-the worst

e.g. she is my best friend.

Adverbs are used to identify verbs or clauses in a sentence.

For example, you speak fluently

My brother runs fast.

According to function, it describes how often something happens, or where, position, manner or how something does there are categories of adverbs in English. Such as adverbs of place, manner, time, frequency, and degree.

For example, *my brother will go to Tashkent tomorrow.* (adverb of time)

I am very happy to hear about it. (adverbs of degree)

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